

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF CARBON NANOMATERIAL Z-THREADED CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER LAMINATES AFTER EXPOSURE TO EXTREME ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

Ryan A. Warren¹, Obaidul Hasan² and Kuang-Ting Hsiao³

¹Systems Engineering Program, University of South Alabama
150 Student Services Drive, Shelby Hall 4106. Mobile, Alabama
Email: raw1522@jagmail.southalabama.edu

²William B. Burnsed, Jr. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Aerospace, and Biomedical Engineering, University of South Alabama
150 Student Services Drive, Shelby Hall 3128. Mobile, Alabama
Email: oh2321@jagmail.southalabama.edu

³William B. Burnsed, Jr. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Aerospace, and Biomedical Engineering, University of South Alabama
150 Student Services Drive, Shelby Hall 3128. Mobile, Alabama
Email: kthsiao@southalabama.edu

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ABSTRACT

Previous studies have shown that carbon nanofiber (CNF) z-threaded carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (ZT-CFRP) laminates exhibit improved mechanical performance in comparison to traditional carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates when exposed to extreme elevated temperatures. Z-threaded reinforcement is a technique for strengthening the through-thickness of a laminate by introducing perpendicularly aligned carbon nanomaterial to be threading into the continuous fiber array. Improved performance has already been observed in properties such as interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) without extreme heat exposure, but there has also been evidence that z-thread inclusion may mitigate strength loss due to thermal degradation of the matrix. This study examined how ILSS was diminished in both CFRP and ZT-CFRP samples with matrix degradation caused by extreme temperature exposure. Test samples were heated to 350 °C for 10 minutes and then allowed to return to room temperature. SBS testing in accordance with ASTM D2344 was conducted on both untreated and heat-treated samples for comparison. All samples were at room temperature during testing. It was found that ZT-CFRP samples (with 0.5wt% CNF concentration the matrix) exhibited higher ILSS with and without heat treatment over the traditional CFRP samples with and without heat treatment by +33.96% and +25.12%, respectively. ZT-CFRP ILSS was found to decrease by 10.584 MPa (-14.56%) after the extreme heat treatment, while CFRP ILSS decreased by only 4.627 MPa (-8.53%). Microscopic image analysis was also performed to provide insight into how the CNF z-threads may have provided a mechanism for retaining ILSS performance even with matrix thermal degradation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The high strength-to-weight ratios of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) have caused it to become an increasingly used and researched material for structural designs. One of the disadvantages of CFRP is that they are anisotropic, with higher mechanical performance being restricted to loadings acting in the direction of the embedded reinforcing fibers. Even with the use of different stacking orientation techniques that can introduce more planar isotropy tendencies, there is still no reinforcing mechanism along the through-thickness of the composite. All reinforcement is confined to the plane of the fiber arrays. The novel Z-threaded nanomaterial reinforcement technique is a proven method for

increasing the through-thickness capabilities of CFRP. Within Z-threaded CFRP (ZT-CFRP), carbon nanomaterial is aligned and threaded perpendicularly through the reinforcing fiber array. A depiction of the concept of ZT-CFRP is provided in Figure 1 with carbon nanofibers (CNF) acting as the nanomaterial reinforcement.

Figure 1: Illustration of ZT-CFRP showing how the nanomaterial reinforcement is threaded perpendicularly through fiber array.

Previous studies have already shown that ZT-CFRP exhibits improved through-thickness dependent material properties in comparison to traditional CFRP composites. This includes strengthened mechanical properties such as Mode-I delamination toughness [1] and longitudinal compressive strength [2], along with improved electrical [3, 4] and thermal conductivities [5]. Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) is a mechanical property that saw significant increase in performance in comparison to traditional CFRP. With the inclusion of 1 wt% CNF z-threads, a 17% improvement in ILSS was observed. Traditional CFRP samples exhibited an average ILSS of 64.89 MPa while ZT-CFRP samples exhibited an average of 75.92 MPa [6].

Improved flammability characteristics have also been observed in ZT-CFRP using UL-94 testing, a standard for assessing the fire hazard of plastic materials. It was shown that ZT-CFRP took on average only 34.95 seconds to self-extinguish, while CFRP samples took on average 86.8 seconds. Self-extinguishing time for ZT-CFRP took only 40% of the time it took for CFRP samples. ZT-CFRP also showed a reduced chance of flame propagation in comparison to CFRP. None of the ZT-CFRP samples burned all the way to the clamp holding the specimen during testing, whereas 60% of the CFRP samples did [7].

A previous study on ILSS failure performance during extreme heat exposure provided evidence of improved strength capabilities and retention in extreme temperature environments of ZT-CFRP in comparison to CFRP. In this study an apparatus was designed and used to replicate the loading of a short beam shear (SBS) test within a muffle furnace chamber. Both CFRP and ZT-CFRP samples were placed inside the apparatus within the chamber and a static loading was exerted onto them. The temperature of the furnace was allowed to increase based on a consistent heating schedule until failure was observed within the testing samples. It was observed that the average failure temperature range for ZT-CFRP was between 384.0 °C to 398.4 °C, whereas CFRP samples failed on average at temperatures ranging from 349.6 °C to 368.2 °C. This was an approximate 30 °C increase in temperature handling capabilities exhibited by ZT-CFRP over CFRP [8].

Based on the temperature failure ranges observed from the previously mentioned study, there is evidence that ZT-CFRP may be better equipped at retaining strength during thermal degradation caused by extreme temperature exposure in comparison to traditional CFRP. This study examined the

retention of ILSS between CFRP and ZT-CFRP when exposed to extreme elevated temperatures that can cause thermal degradation within the matrix. This was accomplished by heat treating specimens at 350 °C within a muffle furnace for 10 minutes. The treated specimens were then removed and underwent SBS testing to experimentally determine their ILSS. Specimens subjected to no heat treatment were also tested to show how much strength was lost due to heat exposure and potential matrix degradation. Specimens for both cases were prepared and tested based on the specifications provided in ASTM D2344 [9]. Microscopic image analysis was also performed to determine how the z-threaded CNF microstructure may have contributed to the failure observed. The process of manufacturing and testing the specimens, testing data, and microscope images of the specimens are provided within this document.

1.1 Review of the Effect of Extreme Temperature Exposure on CFRP Behavior

Quintiere et al. [10] reported that the typical temperature range for the degradation of common aerospace CFRP composites is between 300 °C to 500 °C. The reduction in material properties observed at these elevated temperatures is not only due to the weakening molecular bonds but is also a result of the internal pressure caused by resin vaporization and the reinforcing fibers that hinder its escape. Bazli et al. [11] reported a similar degradation temperature range while also observing that composites loaded in either shear or compression failed at much earlier temperatures in comparison to those loaded in tension or flexure. Ningyun and Evans [12] performed short beam shear tests on fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites between 20 °C and 300 °C. Failure at low temperatures was found to be largely due to interlaminar shear and delamination. Large-scale inelastic deformation was observed within the test specimens at higher temperatures. These studies provide evidence that matrix sensitive material properties are more sensitive to extreme temperatures.

Nema et al. [13] found that both flexural strength and ILSS decreased linearly as temperature was increased to 200°C. Significant decreases in flexural modulus were also observed at around 200 °C which was above the glass transition temperatures of the resin systems being used. Hegde et al. [14] also observed that composite strength and stiffness consistently fell as temperature began to approach the glass transition temperature. With steel and CFRP double strap joints, Nguyen et al. [15] saw load carrying capabilities diminish by 30% when exposed to temperatures around the glass transition temperature.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Materials

All testing specimens utilized unidirectional HexTow AS7 carbon fiber from Hexcel with a density and areal weight of 1.79 g/cm³ and 190 g/m², respectively, for reinforcement. The tow size was 12 K. CNFs used for z-thread nanomaterial reinforcement were PR-24-XT-PS grade from Pyrograph/Applied Sciences Incorporated. This grade of nanofibers was reported to have an average diameter of 100 nm and lengths ranging between 50 μm to 200 μm. The base resin system utilized for all specimens consisted of a mixture of Epon-862, a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F, and Epikure-W, a non-MDA aromatic amine curing agent containing diethylmethylenediamine, both purchased from Miller-Stephenson Chemical Company. The surfactants Disperbyk-191 and Disperbyk-192, both purchased from BYK USA, were used in cases with CNF reinforcement to better disperse the nanomaterial within the resin mixture.

2.2 Prepreg Production

Two different cases of composite panels were manufactured for this study: control containing no nanomaterial reinforcement and ZT-CFRP. All prepreg used for the panels was manufactured through a proprietary production process developed by the Hsiao research group at the University of South Alabama that is illustrated within a pending patent application US20240149541A1 [16]. Both control and ZT-CFRP utilized a base blend of Epon-862 and Epikure-W mixed at a stoichiometric ratio of

100:26.5, respectively. For the ZT-CFRP prepreg, CNF was added at 0.5 wt% of the overall resin matrix mixture. Both Disperbyk-191 and Disperbyk-192 were added at a ratio of 1:1:1 with CNF for better dispersion within the mixture. The resin mixture used for control prepreg manufacturing only contained Epon-862 and Epikure-W.

Both the control and ZT-CFRP resin mixture underwent five minutes of manual stirring once the components were measured out and combined as appropriate. For the ZT-CFRP mixture that contained nanomaterial reinforcement and surfactants, one hour of high shear mixing at 900 rpm using a Stir-Pack Laboratory Mixer was performed. The rotational direction of the mixer was alternated after 30 minutes. The high shear mixed reinforced resin then underwent two hours of sonication using a QSONICA Q700 sonicator. This step was taken to further disperse and reduce agglomerations of CNF within the resin mixture. A sample of the resin mixture was taken after this step to determine the quality of CNF dispersion underneath a Nikon Eclipse LV 150 microscope. Figure 2 provides an image of the final CNF dispersion quality within the resin mixture prior to moving to the next step of prepreg production.

Figure 2: A microscope image showing dispersion quality of the CNF within the resin blend prior to prepreg manufacturing.

The appropriate amount of Epikure-W curing agent was added and manually stirred for 5 minutes into the dispersed CNF mixture to begin the B-staging process. The blend was then placed for approximately 1 hour inside a vacuum oven at 110 °C and -0.09 MPa. The vacuum applied to the resin during this process allowed for the removal of any trapped air within the mixture while also allowing it to partially cure. The control resin mixture also underwent the same B-staging process once Epikure-W was added.

The partially cured resin mixtures were then used in the proprietary ZT-CFRP prepreg production line to create hot melt resin films. An additional alignment process was performed to orientate the CNF reinforcement within the ZT-CFRP film. Alignment is accomplished through reinforced film

exposure to an electrical field for 150 seconds. The hot melt films created for both cases were then used to impregnate dry AS7 fiber fabric arrays. The alignment quality of the created ZT-CFRP prepreg was checked underneath a microscope. An example image of aligned prepreg is provided in Figure 3. Figure 4 provides a diagram detailing the process of making prepreg from start to finish.

Figure 3: A microscope image of CNF alignment between carbon fibers (lines that are running horizontally) taken from a cured sample of prepreg

Figure 4: The prepreg making process is detailed in the diagram from preparing the resin blend to making prepreg.

2.3 Composite Panel and Test Specimen Production

The prepreg for both cases was cut into 127 mm x 127 mm sheets. Prepreg stacks of 16 plies were prepared by hand for both test cases. The prepreg was laid unidirectionally for both cases. The stacks were then cured using the out-of-autoclave vacuum bag-only (OOA-VBO) process detailed in Figure 5. In this process, an individual stack of prepreg is placed onto a release agent coated metal plate and is then covered by a vacuum bag after the peel ply, breather fabric, and other components are laid sequentially as shown in Figure 5. A vacuum pressure of -0.09 MPa was applied to the OOA-VBO assembly. A hot press was utilized to provide the necessary curing temperatures. The hot press was only used to simulate an oven and did not exert any force onto the OOA-VBO assembly. The temperatures and pressures utilized during the curing cycle for both composite panels are provided in Table 1.

Figure 5: The OOA-VBO assembly and components are detailed in the diagram.

Composite Laminate Curing Cycle		
Time	Temperature	Vacuum Applied
60 minutes	22 °C (Room Temperature)	Yes
120 minutes	120 °C	Yes
360 minutes	180 °C	No

Table 1: The curing cycle that was utilized for manufacturing both the control and ZT-CFRP composites used in this study.

Once fully cured, the 127 mm x 127 mm laminate panels were cut to produce samples that fulfilled the criteria specified by the ASTM D2344 standard for SBS testing of fiber reinforced composites. The standard recommends the ratio between specimen thickness, width, and length should be 1:2:6, respectively [9]. With 16 plies, the nominal thickness of the two composite panels made for this study was 2.5 mm. Based off the recommendation by ASTM D2344, the dimensions of the test specimens were approximately 2.5 mm x 5 mm x 15 mm. The 15 mm length was parallel with the direction of the fibers. The ASTM D2344 standard requires that at least five specimens for each case are tested.

2.4 Specimen Heat Treating

An FB1400 model muffle furnace made by Barnstead Thermolyne Corporation was used for heat treating the test samples at 350 °C. The chamber was first preheated to 370 °C. The test specimens were put on a ceramic tray to be inserted within the chamber of the furnace. Once the chamber temperature stabilized, the ceramic tray with the specimens was placed inside the furnace. After two minutes of the ceramic tray being placed inside the chamber and the furnace door closing, the temperature setting of the oven was reduced to 350 °C. This heating procedure allowed the temperature of the specimens to rapidly increase to and hold at the desired exposure temperature of 350 °C. After 10 minutes within the furnace chamber, the ceramic tray and specimens were removed and allowed to cool to room temperature. Only five specimens at a time were heated within the furnace.

2.5 SBS Testing

The short beam shear tests done for this study were done using a Tinius Olsen 10ST universal testing machine. The loading nose and supports of the testing apparatus were both in compliance with ASTM D2344 with diameters of 6 mm and 3mm, respectively. The ASTM D2344 requires that the ratio between span length, or the distance between supporting pins, be four times the thickness of the testing specimen [9]. Since the testing specimens used in this study had a nominal thickness of 2.5mm, the span length was set to 10 mm. The crosshead movement rate of the loading nose was also in compliance and set at a rate of 1.0 mm/min. Data on the position of the loading crosshead and force during testing was output. Figure 6 provides a picture of the testing setup used for this study.

Figure 6: Photo of the SBS setup that was used for this study with a sample loaded.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Testing Data

The force testing output data was used to find the interlaminar shear stress acting on the specimens during SBS testing using the following formula from ASTM D2344:

$$F^{sbs} = 0.75 \times \frac{P}{b \times h} \quad (1)$$

Where F^{sbs} is the interlaminar shear stress, P is the force due to the loading, b is the testing specimen width, and h is the testing specimen thickness [9]. The calculated stress values and crosshead displacement data from testing are plotted in Figure 7 for all four cases of specimens tested: control at room temperature, control after being heat treated at 350 °C, ZT-CFRP at room temperature, and ZT-CFRP after being heat treated at 350 °C

Figure 7: Crosshead displacement and interlaminar shear stress curves taken for the tested specimens.

The ILSS for each test sample is recorded in Table 2. The average ILSS for room temperature and 350 °C treated control CFRP samples was 54.253 MPa and 49.626 MPa, respectively. Based on the average control ILSS values, this was a 4.627 MPa (-8.53%) decline in strength after exposure to 350 °C for 10 minutes. A 10.584 MPa (-14.56%) decline in ILSS was observed between the average for room temperature and 350 °C treated ZT-CFRP samples, which was 72.676 MPa and 62.092 MPa, respectively. At room temperature, the average ILSS for ZT-CFRP was 18.423 MPa higher than that of control. Heat treated ZT-CFRP also had a higher average ILSS than heat treated control, with an observed 12.466 MPa difference between the two. It is interesting to note that the treated ZT-CFRP still had a higher ILSS (62.092 MPa) than that of the control CFRP without exposure of heat treatment (54.253 MPa).

ILSS (MPa)							
Room Temperature				350 °C Treatment			
Control 1	55.254	ZT-CFRP 1	75.308	Control 1	53.591	ZT-CFRP 1	62.759
Control 2	54.925	ZT-CFRP 2	74.606	Control 2	52.779	ZT-CFRP 2	62.882
Control 3	53.876	ZT-CFRP 3	69.317	Control 3	52.251	ZT-CFRP 3	65.525
Control 4	51.776	ZT-CFRP 4	70.564	Control 4	42.948	ZT-CFRP 4	56.413
Control 5	55.432	ZT-CFRP 5	73.584	Control 5	46.560	ZT-CFRP 5	62.880
AVERAGE	54.253	AVERAGE	72.676	AVERAGE	49.626	AVERAGE	62.092
Improvement	-		+33.96%		-		+25.12%
ST DEV	1.350	ST DEV	2.333	ST DEV	4.161	ST DEV	3.024

Table 2: ILSS values recorded for all tested specimens.

3.2 Microscope Image Analysis

Tested specimens were viewed underneath a Nikon Eclipse LV 150 microscope to provide a visualization of what mechanisms may have contributed to the interlaminar failure and strength discrepancies between the four test cases observed. Figure 8 provides images taken along the end of two specimens: one control and one ZT-CFRP that received no heat treatment. As can be seen, a much smaller interlaminar crack formed within the ZT-CFRP sample in comparison to the control sample.

This was likely due to the reinforcing CNF z-threads that helped to resist the formation and propagation of a larger scale crack.

Figure 8: Images taken along interlaminar crack formed on the end of room temperature tested Control Sample 3 (*left*) and ZT-CFRP Sample 5 (*right*).

Figure 9: Images taken along interlaminar crack formed on the end of 350 °C treated tested Control Sample 1 (*top*) and ZT-CFRP Sample 1 (*bottom*).

Figure 9 shows images taken from two 350 °C pretreated samples: one control and one ZT-CFRP. As can be seen within the images taken along the interlaminar crack formation, the ZT-CFRP sample had a much more jagged edge in comparison to the control sample. Exposed CNF z-threads can also

be seen along the length of the crack formation. There also appears to be more misaligned carbon fibers near the interlaminar crack with the ZT-CFRP sample. The jagged edge, exposed z-threads, and greater fiber misalignment of the ZT-CFRP samples may help to support the argument made in the preceding paragraph that the CNF z-threads act as anchoring mechanism that resists delamination and interlaminar failure. The control samples only have the strength of the epoxy bond between layers to prevent delamination.

4 CONCLUSION

This study examined how the inclusion of CNF z-threads contributed to the retention of ILSS within CFRP composites after they have been exposed to extreme elevated temperatures. It was found that ZT-CFRP exhibited improved ILSS over traditional CFRP both with and without extreme temperature exposure. ZT-CFRP exhibited an average ILSS of 72.676 MPa without heat exposure and 62.092 MPa with a 350 °C heat treatment. The traditional CFRP samples exhibited an average ILSS of 54.253 MPa without heat exposure and 49.626 MPa with a 350 °C heat treatment. From the obtained ILSS data and microscope images taken of tested samples, there is evidence to suggest that the CNF z-threads provided a reinforcing mechanism that resisted interlaminar failure and crack propagation of the composite. This could be seen well in the extreme heat-treated samples where there was a diminished matrix due to thermal degradation. The CNF z-threads were apparent along the edges of the formed cracks and were likely significant contributors for ZT-CFRP heat treated samples still having higher ILSS than traditional CFRP samples that received no extreme heat exposure.

It was expected that the traditional CFRP samples would have a more diminished ILSS after heat exposure than was observed. This may have been a result of the CFRP samples being more resin dry in comparison to the ZT-CFRP samples despite having similar dimensions and being composed of the same amount of prepreg plies. There may have already been areas of diminished matrix in the CFRP samples in comparison to the ZT-CFRP samples that would not have been as affected by thermal degradation caused by the elevated temperatures.

The claims made in this publication can be further supported through additional testing in the future. Unaligned CNF reinforced CFRP would help to show that it is the z-threads and not just nanomaterial reinforcement that improves the ILSS capabilities. However, this has already been shown in samples with no extreme heat exposure [6]. Testing different exposure temperatures and/or times would also provide more insight into the effect of thermal degradation of the matrix on CFRP and ZT-CFRP interlaminar strength capabilities. Different CNF weight fractions could also better show the significance of z-threads for strength retention with smaller weight fractions likely not being able to retain ILSS as well as higher weight fractions.

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